

ON RUSSO'S CONJECTURE ABOUT PRIMES

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Abstract . Let n, k be positive integres with $k > 2$, and let b be a positive number with $b \geq 1$. In this paper we prove that if $n > C(k)$, where $C(k)$ is an effectively computable constant depending on k , then we have $C(n, k) < 2/k^b$.

Key words . Russo's conjecture, prime, gap, Smarandache constant.

For any positive integer n , let $P(n)$ be the n -th prime. Let k be a positive integer with $k > 1$, and let

$$(1) \quad C(n, k) = (P(n+1))^{1/k} - (P(n))^{1/k}.$$

In [2], Russo has been conjectured that

$$(2) \quad C(n, k) < \frac{2}{k^{2a}},$$

where $a = 0.567148130202017746468468755\dots$ is the Smarandache constant. In this paper we prove a general result as follows.

Theorem. For any positive number b with $b \geq 1$, if $k > 2$ and $n > C(k)$, where $C(k)$ is an effectively computable constant depending on k , then we have

$$(3) \quad C(n, k) < \frac{2}{k^b}.$$

Proof . Since $k > 2$, we get from (1) that

$$(4) \quad C(n, k) < \frac{2}{k^b} \left[\frac{(P(n+1) - P(n))k^{b-1}}{2(P(n))^{2/3}} \right].$$

By the result of [1], we have

$$(5) \quad P(n+1)-P(n) < C'(t)(P(n))^{11/20+t},$$

for any positive number t , where $C'(t)$ is an effectively computable constant depending on t . Put $t=1/20$. Since $k \geq 3$ and $(k-1)/k \geq 2/3$, we see from (4) and (5) that

$$(6) \quad C(n, k) < \frac{2}{k^b} \left[\frac{C'(1/20) k^{b-1}}{2(P(n))^{1/15}} \right].$$

Notice that $C'(1/20)$ is an effectively computable absolute constant and $P(n) > n$ for any positive integer n . Therefore, if $n > C(k)$, then $2(P(n))^{1/15} > C'(1/20)k^{b-1}$. Thus, by (6), the inequality (3) holds. The theorem is proved.

References

- [1] D.R. Heath-Brown and H. Iwaniec, On the difference between consecutive primes, Invent. Math. 55 (1979), 49-69.
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